

Synthesis and characterization of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes of tridentate Schiff bases

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Abstract : Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes of tridentate Schiff bases with NNO donor set, derived from 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes, have been synthesized and characterized by usual methods and their microbial studies were made.

Keywords : Schiff bases, cobalt(II) complexes, nickel(II) complexes, synthesis.

Our earlier communication¹ deals with spectral and thermal analyses, and evaluation of antibacterial activity of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of tridentate Schiff bases (HL) derived from 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes. The complexes possess 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry, an octahedral geometry and exhibit good antibacterial activity. In this communication, we report synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of the following thiazole Schiff bases. The ligand field energy parameters have been calculated from the electronic spectra of the complexes. The TG curve of a representative Co^{II} complex has been critically analyzed to estimate various kinetic parameters using Coats-Redfern, MacCallum-Tanner and Freeman-Carroll method. The Ni^{II} complexes showed enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to their parent ligands.

Results and discussion

The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are reddish-brown and yellow-green colored crystalline solids respectively. They are soluble in chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene and undergo decomposition above 200 °C. The elemental analyses data (Table 1) suggests 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The molecular weight determinations and very low molar conductance values (< 10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in nitrobenzene indicate that the complexes are monomeric and non-electrolytic in nature.

HL	R	R'
1	Br	H
2	Br	5-CH ₃
3	Br	4-CH ₃
4	Br	3-CH ₃
5	Br	5-Br
6	Br	5-Cl
7	Br	

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands at ~8600, ~18000, ~20000 and ~26000 cm⁻¹. Occurrence of first three bands, attributing to transitions ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} (P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_3)$ respectively, suggests an octahedral geometry for the complexes. An intense band at ~26000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon \sim 1000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) may be due to ligand to metal (metal \leftarrow ligand) charge transfer. The Ni^{II} complexes display bands at ~8000, ~13500, ~24000 and ~26000 cm⁻¹. First three bands, corresponding to transitions ${}^3T_{2g} (F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^3T_{2g} (F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and

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Table 1. Elemental analyses and magnetic moment data of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	R	R'	M% Found (Calcd.)	C% Found (Calcd.)	H% Found (Calcd.)	N% Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
1.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	H	7.50 (7.60)	49.60 (49.55)	2.60 (2.58)	7.35 (7.22)	4.90
2.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-CH ₃	7.25 (7.34)	50.70 (50.81)	3.10 (2.99)	6.90 (6.97)	5.10
3.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	4-CH ₃	7.40 (7.34)	50.95 (50.81)	2.90 (2.99)	6.93 (6.97)	4.98
4.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	3-CH ₃	7.43 (7.34)	50.75 (50.81)	2.91 (2.99)	7.05 (6.97)	5.12
5.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-Br	6.40 (6.31)	41.20 (41.16)	2.00 (1.93)	6.10 (6.00)	4.88
6.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{BrClN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-Cl	6.88 (6.98)	45.60 (45.50)	2.20 (2.13)	6.60 (6.63)	5.10
7.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br		6.68 (6.73)	54.80 (54.86)	2.80 (2.74)	6.50 (6.40)	5.16
8.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	H	7.50 (7.57)	49.50 (49.56)	2.60 (2.58)	7.20 (7.22)	3.12
9.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-CH ₃	7.25 (7.31)	50.85 (50.82)	2.93 (2.99)	7.01 (6.97)	3.00
10.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	4-CH ₃	7.35 (7.31)	50.80 (50.82)	2.90 (2.99)	6.90 (6.97)	3.15
11.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	3-CH ₃	7.40 (7.31)	50.88 (50.82)	2.92 (2.99)	6.92 (6.97)	3.10
12.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-Br	6.35 (6.29)	41.25 (41.17)	2.01 (1.93)	6.15 (6.00)	3.17
13.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{BrClN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br	5-Cl	6.90 (6.96)	46.60 (45.51)	2.10 (2.13)	6.70 (6.63)	3.14
14.	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS})_2$	Br		6.68 (6.71)	54.80 (54.87)	2.65 (2.74)	6.50 (6.40)	3.16

${}^3T_{2g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(v_3)$ respectively, indicate an octahedral geometry for the complexes. The band occurring at $\sim 26000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is sharp and intense ($\epsilon \sim 1000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and may be due to ligand to metal (metal \leftarrow ligand) charge transfer. Racah parameter B , nephelauxetic ratio β and other spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 2.

The infrared spectra of the ligands and that of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have been compared. Thiazole ring and phenyl ring vibrations occurs at $\sim 1600\text{m}$ $\sim 1530\text{m}$, $\sim 1480\text{m}$, $\sim 1450\text{m}$, $\sim 1430\text{m} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands and the complexes (m indicates medium absorption band). The ligands exhibit ν_{OH} , $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes at ~ 2900

(a broad and weak band due to phenolic OH group suggesting an intramolecular hydrogen bonding between -OH and azomethine nitrogen), ~ 1630 and $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively and these values are in agreement with the earlier reported data². The absence of ν_{OH} mode in the complexes indicates the involvement of phenolic -OH in metal-oxygen bond formation. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes in the complexes occur at ~ 1580 and $\sim 1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and shifting of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ towards higher frequency in the complexes, as compared to the ligands, indicate that coordination to the central metal takes place through oxygen of the phenolic OH and nitrogen of the azomethine group². The values of magnetic moments (Gouy) of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes (cm⁻¹)

Sl. no.	Compd.	R	R'	10Dq	B	β_{35}	ν_3/ν_1	ν_2/ν_1	ν_3/ν_2
1.	Co(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	H	9758	837	0.86	2.33	2.13	1.08
2.	Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-CH ₃	8813	787	0.81	2.35	1.95	1.20
3.	Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	4-CH ₃	9762	844	0.87	2.34	2.14	1.09
4.	Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	3-CH ₃	9856	709	0.73	2.33	2.19	1.06
5.	Co(C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Br	9641	823	0.85	2.32	2.13	1.09
6.	Co(C ₁₆ H ₉ BrClN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Cl	9749	823	0.85	2.30	2.13	1.08
7.	Co(C ₂₀ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br		9693	819	0.84	2.30	2.13	1.08
8.	Ni(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	H	8000	840	0.80	2.91	1.65	1.76
9.	Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-CH ₃	8000	866	0.83	2.96	1.66	1.78
10.	Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	4-CH ₃	8100	860	0.83	2.93	1.66	1.77
11.	Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	3-CH ₃	8100	873	0.84	2.95	1.66	1.78
12.	Ni(C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Br	8000	886	0.85	2.99	1.67	1.80
13.	Ni(C ₁₆ H ₉ BrClN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Cl	8100	886	0.85	2.98	1.66	1.79
14.	Ni(C ₂₀ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br		8100	867	0.83	2.91	1.66	1.75

lie in the range 4.8–5.2 and 3.0–3.2 B.M. respectively. These values support the octahedral geometry proposed for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes.

We have reported here antibacterial activity of the ligands and their Ni^{II} complexes against *Salmonella typhi* by serial dilution technique³ in DMF in the concentration range 5–50 µg/ml. We found that MIC values of the ligands and their Ni^{II} complexes lie in the 20–25 and 10–12 µg/ml respectively. The enhanced activity of Ni^{II} complexes, as compare to the ligands, is explained on the grounds of chelation theory⁴.

The Co^{II} complexes are characterized by thermal analysis. We have chosen a representative complex Co(C₁₆H₁₁N₂OS)₂, R = H and R' = H, for study. There is no weight loss upto 190 °C and this rules out presence of any water molecule in the complex. The complex undergoes decomposition in two stages : stage I (288–368°), corresponding to 26% weight loss and stage II (508–724°), 47% weight loss. The residue 11% (theoretical value 12.14% weight) remaining at the end of second stage corresponds to CoO. Thus the complex is found to be thermally stable.

Conclusion :

The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are monomeric, non-electrolytic and covalent in nature having 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry and an octahedral geometry. The coordination takes place through oxygen of phenolic OH, nitrogen of azomethine group and nitrogen of thiazole moiety and thus the ligands behave as tridentate with NNO donor set. The *hx* values indicate that the ligands

should be placed in between urea and ammonia in the nephelauxetic series. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibit enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to their parent ligands. Thermal studies of the Co^{II} complex indicate that the complex is thermally stable.

Experimental

The elemental analyses, molecular weight determination, electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements, recording of UV-Visible and infrared spectra and thermal analysis were performed as reported earlier¹.

The Schiff bases (1–7) were prepared as reported earlier¹. Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes were prepared as copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes using cobalt(II) acetate and nickel(II) acetate in place of copper and zinc complexes. Yield : ~60% in each case.

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